

The Development Of Self-Government Of The Student in The Educational Process

Svetlana V. Khusainova^a, Natalia A. Shepilova^b, Albina N. Kudyasheva^c, Elena A. Sorokoumova^d, Vera V. Murugova^e and Teymur E. Zulfugarzade^f

^aInstitute of Pedagogic, Psychology and Social Problems of Russian Academy of Education, Kazan, RUSSIA; ^bNosov Magnitogorsk State Technical University, Magnitogorsk, RUSSIA; ^cKazan (Volga region) Federal University, Kazan, RUSSIA; ^dMoscow State Pedagogical University, Moscow, RUSSIA; ^eKazan Cooperative Institute of the Russian University of Cooperation, Kazan, RUSSIA; ^fPlekhanov Russian University of Economics, Moscow, RUSSIA

ABSTRACT

The research urgency is caused by necessity to study and develop the phenomenon of students' self-government, providing their vocational formation. In this regard, this paper aims to identify the internal psychological-pedagogical factors for implementing of self-government of the students through the assessment of their personal-typological peculiarities. A leading approach to the study of this problem is activity-based approach, allowing considering of the manifestation of students' personality characteristics within the educational process. The authors present the results of experimental research of internal factors of students' self-government; reveal the specifics for solution of educational tasks in terms of time; identify criteria of successful task performance by the students; theoretically substantiate conditions for manifestation of self-government of College students. The materials of the paper are of practical significance for educators, psychologists, researchers, engaged in the projecting and implementation of learning activities of College students.

KEYWORDS

Vocational education, student, self-government, training activity, personal characteristics

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Introduction

The complexity of the current situation, the transformation of the social order, reformation in the system of education of Russia, expressed in the change of norms, rules, values, high uncertainty about the future leads to students' anxiety on constructing their own life and their self-governance. Self-

CORRESPONDENCE Svetlana V. Khusainova ✉ sv_husainova@mail.ru

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government is of special interest in the period of vocational training and formation, a growing of a young man, when the willingness develops to functioning in the adult world and the desire appears to make their own decisions and take responsibility for them. The problem of studying of self-government is urgent today, both as for researchers and so for practitioners working in educational institutions who are interested in students' position and their unique development.

We regard self-government as a socio-psychological characteristic of individual students, identifying the changes, necessary efforts (work) in the course of educational activities with the aim of achieving a qualitatively new learning outcomes (Khusainova & Levina, 2016). The stages of self-government are similar in many ways to the cyclical phases of management – "analysis of contradictions, forecasting, goal setting, planning, decision-making, criteria for evaluation, control, correction"; the essential difference consists in the transition from self-government (as needs in improvement) to self-regulation (behavior habit and actions)". The problem of development of students' self-government at the University is providing of a focus of the educational process to the factors of self-development: value orientations and motivational attitudes. We agree with the position of V.G. Maralov (2008) who believes that the ideas of self-development do not contradict, but extend and expand the ideas of personality's development in the educational process; the focus are shifted in favor of "self-construction of personality, which needs to create for this conditions by using self-operating mechanism of the individual and expansion of spheres of life activity, while updating not only cognitive motivation, but the motivation of self-development in all its forms and types".

In recent time the authors studied the elements of the structure of self-government that directly affect human behavior, and the results of his activities (Anokhin, 1978; Bernstein, 1966; Konopkin, 2004; Peisakhov, 1991). In their works the elements of the self-governing structures that have complex interactional nature are identified. Activity is manifested in the form of implementation of some program which is defined by a goal against which its regulation occurs.

The study of the problem of self-government was held in Kazan psychological school by N.M. Peisakhov (2001). G.Sh. Gabdreeva (1991) reveals the features of mental States of the individual, which is capable of self-government. M.N. Shevtsov (2004) held the development of the methodics for "Assessing of the capacity for self-government". We believe that consideration of the manifestations of self-government is possible directly through a property of the individual, as activity anxiety - a feeling of inner tension, aimed to overcome it at the moment. Concerning it we consider the specific organization of student's personality and successful independence in the choice of forms and types of regulatory activity of the entity.

A number of researchers (Meili, 1975; Horney, 1997; Prokhorov, 1997; Khusainova, 2003) notes a negative influence of anxiety as personality traits on the components of any level of activity, whether it's communication, behavior or activity. It is noted that there is a relationship between anxiety and motive of avoiding failures in activities. Besides, anxiety is the result of man's awareness of the inadequacy of a subjective model of future activities and the requirements of the situation. Emotional distress in the case of students' learning are

characterized by their richness and duration of the flow, because the students face up problems that contain new (innovative for them) activities. The response of students on educational tasks' fulfillment may be a reflection of the level of self-government that defines the educational potential. Study of the potential and levels of students' self-development provide the teachers with conditions for projecting and implementation of educational programs.

Materials and methods

Research methods

During research the following methods were used: laboratory experiment; pedagogic observation; testing; methods of practical psychology: the method of specific situations of the activity (procedure) sphere; projective method "Labyrinths of Heckhausen" (Hekhausen, 2003); statistical methods for projective and qualitative processing of the obtained material: content-analysis, mathematical-statistical methods.

The experimental base of the research

A pilot study was conducted in SBEI SVE (state budget educational institution of secondary vocational education) "Kazan medical-pharmaceutical College, SBEI SVE "the Kazan medical College". The study sample includes 57 students of the 1st year and 53 students of the 3d courses of the specialty medical business on the base of the 9th grade. The total number of tested - 110.

The stages of the research

A laboratory experiment was conducted using the method of activity-situation and semantic differential to highlight and substantiate the features of the components of self-government of College students. A classical experiment was carried out, as it was said by P. Fress a "provoked", which is referred to as, as it observes the changes of the independent variable without the intervention of the experimenter, and the experiment allows to establish the presence of previously identified binding fact or phenomenon (Meili, 1975).

In the first phase the questionnaire "Performance anxiety" of S.V. Khusainova (2010) was used. The purpose of the survey is to determine the status of the student through the characteristics of the activity-based anxiety. The questionnaire consists of 30 statements to determine the levels (high, medium, low) of the activity-based anxiety on the base of the assessment of the conditions, for example: inner discomfort, tension, laziness, excessive sweating of hands and so on.

In the second stage, the authors used an adapted version of the methodics "Labyrinths of Heckhausen" that provides a comparison of aspirations and achievements of the student in order to represent the dependence of the activity-based anxiety from the level of aspiration and goal setting, self-regulation and time management and discover the ability to coordinate their actions in accordance with the development of system of self-government.

In the third stage an expert assessment was carried out of the external behavior of students and the manifestation of their self-government relatively to the initial values.

Thus, the task was to measure results' performance in specific activity of solving tasks among students with different levels of activity-based anxiety. As independent variable were the conditions of the manifestations of the students' self-government. Dependent variable is dynamics of development of College students' self-government characteristics.

Results

Diagnosis of the characteristics of students' self-management through the characteristics of the activity-based anxiety

Experimental effects in all groups were held at one and the same time - in the morning. All of the students were not tired and were not uploaded with "yesterday" evening classes. Using the questionnaire "Activity-based anxiety" by S.V. Khusainova (2013), it was able to identify groups of students with high, medium and low level of activity-based anxiety regarding new learning activities. Each of them can be revealed in the temporary, emotional, behavioral, somatic and cognitive aspects. Briefly these levels can be summarized as follows:

High level - psychosomatic discomfort; partial disorganization of behavior. Somatic deviations make it difficult to concentrate on activities. The entity postpones the commencement of activities, cannot select the optimal method of its implementation and begins to make a lot of errors.

The average level – psychosomatic, mobilizing. The entity, experiencing the exhilaration and excitement is able to focus on its implementation, resulting in increased efficiency.

Low level– mental level, emotional reaction is positive, the entity refuses to perform activities, or begins to perform it confidently, knowing that he has enough information and experience in a particular activity (see Figure 1)

Figure 1. The distribution of students' experimental group according the characteristics of the activity-based anxiety.

Diagnosis of students' self-managerial manifestation in the course of experimental tasks

The projective method "Labyrinths of Heckhausen" was used the passing (following-up) of which was similar to the solution of the problem for thinking or a kind of puzzle. The method is aimed at the identifying of the degree of students' deviation from the educational goals and allows studying pedagogical situations for solving creative problems, to reflect the activity of the learning and development of self-government, to fix these symptoms on an emotional level and in the behavior of College student.

The experimenter takes into account the time index, which is compared with the planned one in each sample while achieving results. The result of a deviation from the goal in average should not exceed 5-6 points. Next, to determine differences in the effectiveness of the results obtained by the method of "Labyrinths" the Sigma scale should be constructed. (figure 2).

Figure 2. Sigma scale of distribution of the experimental data. (Here \bar{x} – the average arithmetic value of the characteristic for the given age-sex group; σ – standard deviation).

When increasing the number of tested the results of a homogeneous group tend to a normal distribution. The distribution of results is close to normal. Table 1 presents a scale of comparative norms of efficiency of learning tasks' solving.

Table 1. Scale of Comparative Norms.

Ratings	Points	Borders
very high	7	Below 14
high	6	From 14 до 19
above the average	5	From 19 до 21,5
medium	4	From 21,5 до 26,5
below the average	3	From 26,5 до 31,5
low	2	From 31,5 до 34
very low	1	Higher 34

Analysis of experimental data on the projective method of Heckhausen "Labyrinths" has shown that ten 1st year students (38,5%) showed a more

successful time of passing the first part of the experiment with 19 seconds according to the norms of the passing show 5 points, i.e. have a rating of above average. After the informing about the normative time they pass the labyrinth for 17 seconds – this is 6 points, and shows the high evaluation of the passage of labyrinths and increase their abilities in the orientation on the normalized result of the social group.

The 3rd year students with low and medium level of activity-based anxiety, 9 people (35,5%), pass labyrinths of the first half of the experiment for 21, 1 second-4 points, which tells about the average rating of the passage. The second part of the experiment students carry out for 15.3 s. – 6 points, that shows the high assessment of the passage of labyrinths and not only take into account the normalized result of the social group, but also can improve it at the expense of their possibilities to take into account the time of work in a short time.

The combined results demonstrate that students with a high level of activity-based anxiety make more moves and less effectively solve problems, and students with low and medium level of activity-based anxiety in the beginning make a lot of moves, but in the end bring the solution of tasks to the minimum number of moves. Students with middle-and low level of activity-based anxiety are able to accumulate experience in solving problems that is manifested in the reduction of the number of moves, in contrast to students with a high level of activity-based anxiety. The data obtained allow determining of the state (levels) of self-government for each student with the goal to develop and enhance performance of learning and quality of education.

Expert assessment of manifestations of students' self-governance within learning tasks

As experts the teachers, psychologists, medical professionals acted. Their task consisted in the joint estimation of personal characteristics that revealed the state of students' self-management at the beginning, middle and end of the experiment (in progress). It was recorded that:

- in the first year, at the beginning of the experiment, the students "flexibility" is most pronounced (av.=3,9), providing the adaptation of students to new learning activities, new learning environment;

- in the first year, in the middle of the experiment, the students' confidence (av. = 3,9) and flexibility (av. = 3,9) are mostly expressed, indicating a decrease in fear, stress before a new activity, the manifestations of entity-entity relations in training, willingness to cooperate;

- in the first year, at the end of the experiment, the students "concentration" (av. = 3,9), and "creativity" (av. = 4) are mostly expressed, demonstrating the concentration of the student on the learning activity and readiness for the manifestation of creative qualities;

- in the third year, at the beginning of the experiment, the students' "determination" was mostly expressed (av.=3,7), enabling them to accept new learning activities as needed, to be ready to tackle new challenges without the fear of them;

- in the third year, in the middle of the experiment, the students' "flexibility" (av. = 4), "autonomy" (av.= 3,6) and "concentration" (av.=3.3 V) are

mostly expressed, that allows to speak about the presence of autonomy in the adoption of the new, the achievement of educational goals;

- in the third year, at the end of the experiment, the students' "concentration" (av.=3,2) and creativity (av. = 3,2) are mostly expressed, which provide the potential for their future vocational activity, readiness to independently solve non-standard tasks.

By the method of expert evaluation, semantic differential it is confirmed that the components of self-government obtained ("flexibility", "autonomy", "focus", "determination", "creativity") of the College students are manifested in situations of direct educational activities in solving difficult problems in the organized conditions of the laboratory experiment. To determine the consistency of expert estimates, the coefficient of concordance of Kendal was applied, which is equal to 0,31261 when $R=0,42$. (tends to one). Average rank = 0.0254.

Based on the results of the ascertaining experiment and interpretation of the results obtained it can be concluded that students with low and middle level of activity-based anxiety, while in terms of normalization, in a situation of frustration, show more effective results and leave less time to pass the labyrinths. Also, if to watch the video, these students are more interested in the result when working with labyrinths and experience satisfaction in obtaining good results. Students with low and middle level of activity-based anxiety are able to accumulate experience in solving problems that is manifested in the reduction of the number of moves, in contrast to students with a high level of activity-based anxiety.

So, in the course of the experiment it is found that the students of the first and third course are able to define their wishes and goals related to future vocational activity and life activity in general. This can characterize the manifestation of self-government, which provides for the formation of a competitive graduate with the necessary personal and vocational qualities, along with the knowledge and competences in professional sphere, enabling them more successfully to adapt to the changing socio-economic conditions. This proves the necessity of creation of psycho-pedagogical conditions in educational activities for development of students' self-management.

Discussion and Conclusion

Thus, performance of activity-based anxiety, understood as a personality's feature and reflecting its level characteristics allows showing a students' conscious self-management of transformational activity in accordance with knowledge about their own capabilities and requirements of real-life situations. This property manifests itself in entity's cognitive, volitional, behavioral spheres according to the abilities and requirements of the situation (Rozhkov & Bayborodova, 2000). It should be noted that there is a discrepancy between the needs of the individual in a variety of life activity and the real educational practice, effectively restricting the activities of the student and, as a rule, focused only on the solution of standard tasks.

The formation of the criteria of students' self-government largely determines his success in various fields of his activity, as it allows him to show independence as an entity of any activity (Khusainova, 2016). The more complex and creative the activity is, the greater the role of self-government in the process of socio-psychological adaptation throughout life. The self-government

contributes to the harmonization of personality, its adequate behavior in society and vocational development.

College students' self-government in term of their life activity ensures the development of their autonomy's development in making and implementing decisions to achieve publically significant objectives (Rozhkov & Baiborodova, 2000) and may contribute to the solution of problems of formation and development of social activity of a person, formation of the future professional. Significant potential in the development of social activity belongs to a College, assuming the training's profile and its practical orientation that necessitates high self-organization, responsibility and activity of students.

The hypothesis of the study is confirmed: the development of self-government of College students will be effective, if self-government: is based on modern psychological and pedagogical approaches to its organization, content and technologies; is determined as a necessary component of teaching and educational work of teachers and psychologists of the educational organization; includes a variety of forms, methods and technologies of training and education; is provided by a complex of psycho-pedagogical support of the educational activities.

The mechanism of development of the self-management is the conscious transformation of "the object into the subject" or "object into entity". And the base of it is a mechanism of identification (correlation of the entity with the subject and their relating of the subject with the entity or coupling them to each other). So can be taken as a basis the mechanism of "interiorization" – "exteriorization" according to L.S. Vygotsky – the transition of external actions into internal plan, and then the translation of internal projects into external actions, especially productive ones (Rubinstein, 1940). The recognition of the objective value and subjective meaning what is made by the man, and then what will be made by the man and how he will be satisfied by the made. In the end, the person realizes his personal satisfaction from the done and begins to realize that he knows his own level of achievement and this helps him to overcome the internal resistance to the implementation of activities.

It is established that the development of College students' self-government will be successful if its development is purposefully organized by teachers in educational and extracurricular activities through a set of learning tasks with significant (for students) novelty items and short run time. While reducing the level of students' activity-based anxiety the inner confidence and readiness for training activity appears.

We believe that it is necessary to continue research on development of the teaching methods for the development of self-government of College students within the academic disciplines.

Disclosure statement

No potential conflict of interest was reported by the authors.

Notes on contributors

Svetlana V. Khusainova – is PhD, Associate Professor, Senior Researcher, Institute of Pedagogy, Psychology and Social Problems of Russian Academy of Education, Kazan, Russia.

Natalia A. Shepilova – is PhD, Associate Professor of the Department of preschool education, Nosov Magnitogorsk State Technical University, Magnitogorsk, Russia.

Albina N. Kudyasheva – is PhD, Associate Professor of the Department of Physical Education and Sport, Kazan (Volga region) Federal University, Kazan, Russia.

Elena A. Sorokoumova – is Doctor Psychology, Professor of the Department of Labor Psychology and Psychological Counseling of Moscow State Pedagogical University, Moscow, Russia.

Vera V. Murugova – is PhD, Associate Professor of Kazan Cooperative Institute (Branch) of the Russian University of Cooperation, Kazan, Russia.

Teymur E. Zulfugarzade – is PhD, Associate Professor of the Department of Civil Law, Plekhanov Russian University of Economics, Moscow, Russia.

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